

Characterisation of dispersed phosphor particles for quantitative photoluminescence measurements

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Abstract

Appropriate characterisation methods are necessary to probe the photoluminescence properties of phosphor particles, in order to develop new and more efficient materials and broaden the scope of their application. In this work, experiments show that relative luminescence signal levels of different phosphor particles obtained from studies of bulk powder bears no relation to the relative signal of the same materials when probed as dilute liquid dispersions. Characterisation of particles suspended in a liquid is shown to deliver appropriate spectroscopic data including the photoluminescence emission intensity per particle, allowing the rapid evaluation of phosphors using milligram quantities of powder. This characterisation technique is relevant to applications involving optically thin arrangements of particles as found in, for example, medical bioimaging, thin coatings for lighting, solar cell sensitisation and temperature measurements in fluids. Quantitative benchmark results are reported for the thermographic phosphors $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, ZnO , $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$, $(\text{Sr},\text{Mg})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2:\text{Sn}^{2+}$, $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$, $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$.

Keywords: Photoluminescence, Quantitative spectroscopy, Phosphor-liquid dispersion, Phosphor powders, Luminescence thermometry, Characterisation methods

1. Introduction

Phosphors are solid crystalline compounds, often doped with transition metal or rare-earth ions, which exhibit the property of luminescence. They are generally produced in fine powder form, i.e. particles with a size spanning nm to 10's μm . Phosphors have an extraordinary range of uses including display technology, lighting such as in white LEDs [1], solid-state and fiber lasers [2], security printing [3], solar cells [4], medical treatment [5] and imaging [6]. For a specific application, from a nearby infinite range of materials a choice must be based on the spectral characteristics, lifetime, and brightness of the luminescence; the material chemical, mechanical and thermal stability; and its availability, cost and ease of manufacture. Finding new or improved materials is important to improve efficiency, broaden the scope of applications and reduce environmental harm by substituting more abundant elements for rare-earths. An integral aspect of this process is the comparison of materials and for this it is clearly of interest to use common characterisation methods that provide the most useful information.

It is well-known that the state of the powder influences the overall optical properties of the material [7]. In the laboratory, often thick layer powders (>100's of μm) are used to compare the photoluminescence emission intensity of materials. In this case, the thickness of the layer is much greater than the penetration depth of the light. Multiple scattering of the light is

significant, and re-absorption of emitted light by the powder itself can occur if there is an overlap between excitation and emission spectra [8]. In the limit of an optically thick powder state, the quantum efficiency will dominate the observed brightness. For example, in lighting applications such as white LEDs, a coating thickness (10's of μm) on the order of the penetration depth is used and the emphasis is placed on colour-rendering and conversion efficiency.

In all but a few applications the strength of the absorption of excitation light must also play an important role. The absorption characteristics of coatings used in white LEDs, for instance, have a direct effect on the ratio of InGaN (blue) emission transmitted to downshifted phosphor emission and therefore the colour coordinates [9]. In several emerging applications, thinner layers of phosphor materials and/or lower density of particles are used, in which case single particle-light interaction events dominate. The geopolitics and environmental impact of rare-earth and transition metal mining also means that the use of smaller quantity of powders in lighting devices is desirable [10]. To improve solar cell efficiency, downconverting, downshifting and upconverting particles can be used to maximise the conversion of radiation from the solar spectrum [4]. In this case, attenuation of solar radiation in the visible range by particle Mie scattering must be minimised so low concentrations of highly absorbing particles in the UV or IR range are needed. In medical treatment and bio-imaging, low concentration of nanoparticles are used [5, 6] and the optical properties of individual particles are also likely to dominate. These applications have significant implications for the characterisation of luminescence properties. Imagining the conceptual limits of

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densely packed powder beds and a single phosphor particle, we should ask whether optical property data extracted from particles assembled in one state are transferable to a situation where the same particles are arranged differently.

Our interest lies in an application belonging to the latter end of said spectrum: temperature sensing in gas and liquid flows [11]. Phosphor particles are introduced into the fluid at low concentrations (typically 0.1-1 mg/L). The temperature of phosphor particles is assumed to match the temperature of the surrounding fluid, and thus by detecting either the temperature-dependence of the photoluminescence (hereafter luminescence) emission spectrum or lifetime upon laser excitation, the fluid temperature can be determined. The abundance of different luminescence properties of phosphors means that the thermometry method can be tuned in terms of spatial/temporal resolution, temperature sensitivity, and temperature range to match the need of specific applications in engineering, biomedicine etc. The temperature is either derived from the emission of single particles for high resolution measurements [12, 13], or from groups of typically less than 100's of particles within an elementary probe volume [14]. High particle concentrations should be avoided so as not to alter the fluid properties or promote multiple scattering which decreases the spatial resolution of the measurements. Maximising the emission intensity of single particles is equally important as maximising the temperature sensitivity of the luminescence emission spectrum or lifetime for thermometry.

So far, only very few of the available materials have been investigated for fluid thermometry. Among the nine phosphors summarised in a recent review article [11], only two of them, $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ (BAM:Eu²⁺) [15] and ZnO [14], have been characterised in adequate detail for use in fluids. Specifically, the luminescence emission intensity per particle and its temperature dependence, the luminescence decay time, the excitation and emission spectra, the temperature sensitivity, the dependence of emission intensity on excitation parameters (laser wavelength, fluence, power density), and some (generally unwanted) possible cross-sensitivities to surrounding fluid composition, laser excitation fluence and particle number density were measured. With these data, the performance of a particular phosphor for fluid temperature measurements in a given situation can be assessed.

Much of the abovementioned data were extracted from studies of phosphor particles dispersed in gas flows. This was done for three reasons. First, because previous studies had determined that irreversible damage, heating, and lasing effects can occur in densely aggregated, packed bulk powder at laser energies normally used in fluid thermometry experiments (>10 mJ/cm²) [11]. Second, studies of known quantities of dispersed particles can provide the signal per particle, using a particle counting system [16], which permits prediction of signal levels in specific applications within the constraints of low particle concentrations.

The third reason returns to the question posed earlier: It is not clear whether even relative luminescence intensities of phosphors in bulk powder form are a reliable indicator of the signal strength when the particles are dispersed in a fluid. Con-

sidering the difference in the optical density of the probe material, simply comparing the luminescence signal of a controlled mass (1 g) of phosphor powders in the bulk may not even be a suitable approach for quickly evaluating potential materials before further characterisation. Every week, at least several articles are published on new phosphors intended for thermometry, usually promising a high temperature sensitivity. Unfortunately, not only do these studies rarely address the state of the powder in relation to the application, they infrequently consider signal level at all, i.e. determine the luminescence signal in comparison to another 'benchmark' sensor material. **For bulk powder applications, an approach similar to that described by Khalid and Kontis [17] should be standardised and systematically applied.**

How should the relevant information be obtained for dispersed particles? Single particle methods using ultrasonic levitation or optical tweezers do not quickly provide the required data averaged over the particle distribution. Casting particles in a transparent polymer is another option [18], but aforementioned heating effects at high excitation irradiances typically used for fluid thermometry could interfere with the measurement. In our previous work, the particles were dispersed in gas flows but this is time-consuming, requires substantial quantities of powder (10's g) using conventional particle seeders, and the seeding density has to be measured since this cannot be easily controlled or held constant. In the course of investigating the use of ZnO particles for liquid thermometry, it was suggested that instead small-volume liquid dispersions might be a more suitable characterisation method [19], requiring smaller amounts of powder (mg), less time, and potentially without need to measure the number of particles, but the validity of this approach has not yet been clearly demonstrated.

In light of these considerations, the objectives of this study are the following. The first is to determine whether there are major differences when comparing the luminescence emission intensity of phosphor samples in thick powder form and phosphor samples dispersed in a fluid. The second is to develop accurate and time-effective methods to extract absolute emission intensity from liquid dispersions in terms of number of photons emitted per unit quantity of phosphor particles, whether by mass or by particle, under a known excitation irradiance. Third is to apply the method to quantify the absolute emission intensities of other phosphor materials that were already used for thermometry but incompletely characterised.

2. Methods

2.1. Phosphor particles

Phosphors were chosen from those often used for fluid thermometry [11]. The materials were acquired from external suppliers as listed in Table 1. The dopant concentrations were determined by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Particle size distributions were either provided by the manufacturer from Coulter counter measurements or taken from literature.

Phosphor	Supplier	Product code
BaMgAl ₁₀ O ₁₇ :Eu ²⁺	PT	KEMK63/UF-P1
ZnO	SA	96479
(Sr,Mg) ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ :Sn ²⁺	OSRAM	SV 253
Mg ₄ FGeO ₆ :Mn ⁴⁺	PT	EQD25/UF-X
Y ₃ Al ₅ O ₁₂ :Pr ³⁺	PT	QMK59/FF-X
Y ₃ Al ₅ O ₁₂ :Dy ³⁺	PT	QMK66/F-X
La ₂ O ₂ S:Eu ³⁺	PT	SKL63/F-R1

Table 1: Phosphor samples used in this study. PT stands for Phosphor Technology Ltd. and SA for Sigma Aldrich.

2.2. Particle dispersions

The method outlined in Ref. [19] was used to prepare the liquid dispersions and is only briefly described here. Phosphor particles were dispersed using an ultrasonic homogeniser (Bandelin Sonopuls HD 2200) and further dilution was used to obtain dispersions at mass loads in the range of 1 to 50 mg/L. The solution was contained in a 28 ml fused silica cuvette (40 (W) × 20 (D) × 35 (H) mm) containing a stirring bar, and placed on a magnetic stirrer and heater plate. During the measurements, the solution was stirred continuously. The repeatability of the dispersion procedure was 10% as determined from the standard deviation of the emission intensity of ten repeat dispersions prepared with the same mass load.

For excitation of the particles the third (355 nm) or fourth (266 nm) harmonics of an Nd:YAG laser (10 ns pulse duration) were used. A 2.1 mm wide and 4.3 mm high (full-width half-maximum) laser beam was formed in the center of the cuvette using a single cylindrical convex lens ($f=50$ mm) as shown in Fig. 1. For the bulk powder comparisons, samples containing 1 g of phosphor particles were placed in a 15 mm diameter ceramic crucible and illuminated with an unfocused laser beam. The laser energy was measured using an energy meter. **For the data presented here, the temperature of all liquid dispersion and bulk powder samples is 298 ± 2 K.**

Figure 1: Experimental setup for characterisation of liquid dispersions

2.3. Quantitative spectroscopy

To acquire luminescence emission spectra, the light emitted by the phosphor dispersions was collected by an objective lens ($f=50$ mm $f/4$) with the front focus plane at infinity and the back focus plane coincident with the entrance slit of an imaging spectrometer (Acton Research SP300i, $f=500$ mm, 300 grooves/mm) as shown in Fig. 1. Spectra were recorded using an interline CCD camera (Imager Pro-X 1200x1600 pixels, $7.4 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size), with the camera exposure set to start $1 \mu\text{s}$ before the laser pulse. The exposure time was adjusted according to the phosphor under study in order to capture the entire luminescence decay.

The recorded images were summed in the vertical direction and from the resulting signal the **spectral radiance** emitted by the phosphor dispersion was calculated. The calculation considered the light collection geometry, losses from the various optical components, and the detector quantum efficiency. The number of photons incident on a column of pixels of the CCD camera corresponding to the wavelength λ , $I(\lambda)$ can be calculated as a function of the time-integrated **spectral radiance** $\Phi(\lambda)$ (photons/m²/steradian/nm/pulse) emitted by a laser-sheet thick area of illuminated particle dispersion as:

$$I(\lambda) = \Phi(\lambda) \times A_e \times \Omega \times \tau(\lambda) \times \Delta\lambda \quad (1)$$

where A_e is the emitting area, Ω the collection solid angle, $\tau(\lambda)$ the transmittance of the optical components, and $\Delta\lambda$ the pixel scaling (in nm per pixel). Considering the geometry of the system (see Fig. 1), the extent of the laser sheet-thick area which is illuminated and from which light is collected by the spectrometer is limited by the lens aperture and the laser sheet height h according to:

$$A_e = \frac{f h}{f_{\#}} \quad (2)$$

where f is the focal length of the objective and $f_{\#}$ its f -stop (set higher or equal to that of the spectrometer). The collection solid angle Ω is:

$$\Omega = \frac{\delta}{f_{\#} o} \quad (3)$$

where δ is the slit width and o is the lens center to object distance. The transmittance $\tau(\lambda)$ was determined by recording spectra of a tungsten lamp which were normalised to match (at the blaze wavelength of 500 nm) the product of the transmittance of the various optical components including that of the lens objective, mirrors and grating, as specified by the manufacturer.

The number of photons emitted per mass of illuminated phosphor particles $N_{ph,m}$ (photons/mg/pulse/nm) was determined from the measured **spectral radiance**, assuming the particle as lambertian emitters:

$$N_{ph,m}(\lambda) = \frac{4\pi \Phi(\lambda)}{t m_L} \quad (4)$$

where t is the laser sheet thickness in the direction of the lens optical axis and m_L the mass load of the particle dispersion.

2.4. Particle counting

Additionally, the number of particles in the probe volume was counted using a high-resolution particle Mie scattering imaging system using a thinner green light sheet, a system detailed in Ref. [16]. The output of a frequency-doubled Nd:YAG laser was formed into a 170 μm -thick light sheet using a $f=1000$ mm cylindrical lens which propagated through the center of the cuvette. The laser fluence at this location was measured to be 70 mJ/cm^2 . Particle images were formed on a small colour camera (Imager E-lite 1.4 M, 1392 x 1040 pixels, 6.45 μm pixel size), equipped with a $f=200$ mm Nikon lens with the f-stop at $f/4$, corresponding to a field of view of approximately 6×8 mm. Only the green channel was used. The images were then processed to identify the number of local maximum using the algorithm described in [16]. The number density of particles in the dispersion n_p was then calculated by dividing the number of counted particles by the size of the counting system probe volume. Combining quantitative spectroscopy and particle counting results, the emission intensity per particle following a single laser pulse $N_{ph,p}$ (photon/particle/pulse/nm) was determined using:

$$N_{ph,p}(\lambda) = \frac{4\pi \Phi(\lambda)}{t n_p}. \quad (5)$$

Note that that spectroscopy and particle counting were performed on two different measurement stations, each with a stirrer plate so that the cuvette containing a dispersion could rapidly be moved from one station to the other. The total measurement time for probing one dispersion including counting and spectroscopy was about 5 minutes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Comparison of aggregate powders and dispersed particles

Initially we examined four phosphor powders: BAM:Eu²⁺, ZnO, Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ (MFG:Mn⁴⁺) and (Sr,Mg)₃(PO₄)₂:Sn²⁺ (SMP:Sn²⁺). The first three powders have been extensively used for thermometry [11], and the fourth has been recently characterised as a sensitive temperature sensor for fluids [20]. The relative emission intensities of each powder were compared in two different states: in liquid dispersions for a prescribed mass load (2-20 mg/L) of particles, and in thick powder layers using a fixed mass (1 g) of particles in a crucible. In each state, the recorded emission spectra were normalised by the mass of particles. Fig. 2 summarises these data, where the emission spectrum of every phosphor has been normalised to the maximum of the emission band of BAM:Eu²⁺ (450 nm) in the relevant powder state.

Most striking is the observation that for the same mass of phosphor in liquid dispersions, the integral ZnO emission is a factor ten *higher* than that of BAM:Eu²⁺, while for thick powder aggregates, the ZnO emission is a factor 50 *lower* than that of BAM:Eu²⁺. This corresponds to a difference of nearly a factor 500 in the relative signal intensity between dispersed and

aggregated powder states. Note that this cannot be due to saturation effects at the higher fluence (20 mJ/cm^2) used for the dispersed particles, since both BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO were proven to have very similar saturation behaviour [15, 14].

We propose the following explanation for this remarkable difference. The relative quantum efficiency of BAM:Eu²⁺ is known to be 1.05 that of MgWO₄ [7] (itself 85% in absolute value [21]). The absorption cross section of Eu²⁺ ions is relatively weak and values in the range 10^{-19} to 10^{-18} cm^2 were observed in NaF, KMgF₃, CaF₂ and KCl [22, 23]. Considering a dopant concentration of 10% this correspond to an absorption coefficient of 3×10^2 cm^{-1} or below. ZnO is markedly different in its absorption and emission characteristics: the absorption coefficient of bulk ZnO is reportedly three orders of magnitude higher than BAM:Eu²⁺ at 3×10^5 cm^{-1} [24], but the absolute quantum efficiency can be below 1% [25]. The mass fraction of phosphor in these liquid dispersions is so low that the solution and pure water are indistinguishable by eye. Moreover, a calculation based on the measured mass load and the absorption coefficient shows that for the most absorbing dispersions (ZnO) attenuation is negligible. These liquid dispersions are therefore optically thin. Assuming a homogeneous medium, the total excitation light absorbed by the phosphor is proportional to the absorption coefficient. The luminescence emission intensity is the product of the absorbed light and the quantum efficiency. Indeed, the measured difference in the total emission intensity of dispersed ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺ particles ($\times 10$) is consistent with the known difference in the absorption coefficient ($\times 1000$) and quantum efficiency (~ 0.01) product.

In the bulk powder, the penetration depth of the excitation light is on the order 100 μm for BAM:Eu²⁺, a value far lower than the depth of the powder layers, which in these experiments is approximately 1 cm. In this optically thick case and again initially considering a homogeneous medium, we can now assume that the same amount of excitation light is absorbed for every phosphor. The relative bulk powder luminescence signals would then reduce to the ratio of quantum efficiencies. The measured ratio in the total emission intensity of ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺ bulk powder (~ 0.02) is commensurate with the literature values (order 0.01).

The analysis can be extended to the results for the two other phosphors MFG:Mn⁴⁺ and SMP:Sn²⁺. The relative quantum efficiencies of both phosphors are reportedly only slightly lower than that of BAM:Eu²⁺ (0.75 and 0.85 for MFG:Mn⁴⁺ and SMP:Sn²⁺ respectively). The integral luminescence signal per unit mass obtained in the liquid dispersion is similar for BAM:Eu²⁺, MFG:Mn⁴⁺ and SMP:Sn²⁺ suggesting that the absorption coefficients of the three materials are a similar order of magnitude. The measured integral luminescence emission intensity per unit mass of bulk powders qualitatively follows the trend in quantum efficiency: the signals of ZnO (~ 0.02), MFG:Mn⁴⁺ (~ 0.28) and SMP:Sn²⁺ (~ 0.35) progressively increase relative to BAM:Eu²⁺. However, these powders are inherently highly scattering media. If excitation light travels farther into the bulk powder, as is the case for MFG:Mn⁴⁺, SMP:Sn²⁺ and BAM:Eu³⁺, multiple scattering could affect the geometry of the excited volume and collection of the emitted luminescence by the spec-

Figure 2: Quantitative photoluminescence emission spectra of $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$, $(\text{Sr,Mg})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2:\text{Sn}^{2+}$ and ZnO obtained from *liquid dispersions* (full line) under an excitation fluence of 20 mJ/cm^2 ; and from *aggregated powders* (dash lines) under an excitation fluence of 1 mJ/cm^2 , both at 266 nm . The emission spectra are normalised to the $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ signal in the corresponding powder state, i.e. dispersed or aggregated.

trometer system. One reason for the lack of quantitative agreement between relative quantum efficiencies of these phosphors and the measured bulk powder luminescence intensities could be the different refractive indices of e.g. germanates (2.2) relative to aluminates (1.78), which will affect the degree of multiple scattering within the powder aggregate.

To summarise, the comparison of luminescence emission intensities between phosphor materials is highly dependent on the state of agglomeration. It is evident that the results of a comparative evaluation of the brightness of aggregate powder samples predominantly compares quantum efficiency only and as such are not transferable to the case of optically thin phosphor layers or dispersed particles. Instead, a quantitative per mass comparison performed on dispersed particles reveals the quantum efficiency-absorption coefficient product which is far more relevant to applications involving optically thin arrangements of particles, such as superresolution microscopy applications in biology, flexible displays, thin coatings for surface thermometry, or fluid thermometry.

3.2. Assessment of liquid dispersion characterisation

The utility of dispersed particle characterisation having been established, it motivates us to consider potential sources of error in the liquid dispersion method and in what way it can be used to extract transferable information. For example, an assumption inherent to the foregoing comparison was that the dispersions were uniformly loaded with particles and that the actual mass load was the same as the mass load measured when preparing the solution. In these experiments a particle counting system was also used to provide an independent measure of the quantity of particles in the probe volume of the spectroscopy.

Since a decline in emission intensity was observed in ZnO dispersions, which were continuously stirred, measurements of the particle number density in the cuvette were performed for three phosphors over a 1500 s duration. The results are shown

Figure 3: Decline in particle number density observed for three phosphor dispersions over the course of 1500 s . Exponential fits are added to guide the eye

in Fig. 3. As shown, the decline in the number density of particle is the most pronounced for the dispersion of ZnO particles with a 50% drop over 500 s . We assume this is due to attraction to the cuvette walls and not to particle settling because the cuvette was stirred continuously, and because the ZnO particles are the smallest and therefore have the lowest settling velocity. From these results, the error in the absolute luminescence intensity measurements of this article is on the order of the steepest decline in particle number density over the 5-minute interval between the counting and spectroscopy measurements, i.e. 40%.

Furthermore, in another set of experiments undertaken with the same mass loads but instead using water from a laboratory purification system, it was observed that the luminescence emission from the ZnO dispersion was reduced by a remarkable two orders of magnitude, and that the signal of $\text{SMP}:\text{Sn}^{2+}$ was around a factor 4 lower. The signal of $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ was how-

ever unchanged. The differences are extraordinary given the repeatability stated above. Again, the particle counting system was employed, and in every case the reduction in luminescence signal closely matched the measured number of particles. The difference is due to phosphor-specific particle surface charge and the overall charge balance in the solution, which sensitively depends on, for example, solution pH [26], and which causes attraction of the particles to the cuvette walls. However, this observation raises the question that the results presented previously could have been influenced by this effect, i.e. that the mass of particles probed in our experiment did not correspond to the originally measured mass.

To verify that this was not the case, the number of particles was also counted in the solutions used for Fig. 2, and the results are shown in Table 2. For similarly sized particles BAM:Eu²⁺, SMP:Sn²⁺ and MFG:Mn⁴⁺, the number of particles in the probe volume is directly proportional to the mass load. The ratio of particles number to mass load is approximately 10 times higher for ZnO, which is expected from the smaller size of the particles. However, the width of the particle size distribution, the difference between number-based distribution and volume-based distributions, and difference in sizing methods prevents a more detailed comparison. Nevertheless, the particle counting demonstrates the consistency of the original dispersions and that the per mass load comparative results presented in Section 3.1 are valid.

Phosphor	particle size μm	mass load mg/L	Particle number density $\times 10^6/\text{cm}^3$
BaMgAl ₁₀ O ₁₇ :Eu ²⁺	2.4	10	2.0
(Sr,Mg) ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ :Sn ²⁺	1.9	20	3.6
Mg ₄ FGeO ₆ :Mn ⁴⁺	2.8	20	4.5
ZnO	1.2	2	3.4

Table 2: Relation between particle size, measured mass load and measured number of particles in the probe volume. Particle sizes are median diameter per volume and were determined using a Coulter counter (BAM:Eu²⁺, SMP:Sn²⁺ and MFG:Mn⁴⁺) or a laser diffraction instrument (ZnO).

This implies that using small liquid volumes for phosphor characterisation cannot necessarily rely on a simple mass measurement to determine the mass-referred signal of particles in the dispersed state. It may be possible to use some pH stabilisation technique, see e.g. Refs. [26, 27], but this would have to be performed for every individual phosphor. In this regard, particle counting is of considerable utility because it is possible to check the measured mass and the actual interrogated mass, although variations of the particle sizing method and accuracy of the size distribution measurement must be considered. Also, some host materials such as sulphates may exhibit some degree of solubility in water and the test liquid must be chosen accordingly. Overall, our system requires only very small (mg) samples of material and rapid investigations of the luminescence signal of many phosphors can be performed in less than a day.

3.3. Quantitative measurements of dispersed phosphor materials

With knowledge of the particle number density, the luminescence emission intensity of a single particle can be extracted using equation 5. This quantity is of fundamental value for several reasons. It directly relates to the signal detected in applications when single particles are probed such as superresolution microscopy [6], or high-resolution fluid temperature measurements approaches which probe individual particles ([12, 13]). In addition, the interaction of individual particles with light is the basic building block to assess denser systems containing more particles. The discrete particulate nature of the sample is important because the overall absorption coefficient is not solely dependent on the volume-average concentration of luminescent centers, as would be the case for fluorescent molecules such as dyes. The absorption coefficient of a sample containing phosphor particles, and therefore the luminescence signal per unit volume, also depends on the size and shape of the particles themselves as well as the refractive index of the medium and particles and the excitation wavelength. Therefore, to obtain results relevant to many of the applications cited in this article, it is necessary to study a stable mass load of dispersed particles with accompanying knowledge of either the particle size distribution or the number density of particles in dispersion. Here we adopt this latter approach to investigate several phosphors previously employed for fluid thermometry.

Fig. 4 summarises the luminescence spectra in terms of photons/particle/nm for ZnO, BAM:Eu²⁺, MFG:Mn⁴⁺, SMP:Sn²⁺, and three other phosphors previously used for thermometry in the gas and liquid phases (see citations summarised in Ref. [11]): Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Pr³⁺ (YAG:Pr³⁺), Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Dy³⁺ (YAG:Dy³⁺), and La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺. Table 3 provides various information about the tested materials (particle size, dopant concentration, luminescence lifetime) and excitation parameters (laser wavelength, chosen to match the excitation spectrum of the material with either the third or fourth harmonics of an Nd:YAG laser, and laser fluence). Table 3 also provides the total number of luminescence photons obtained by integration over selected emission bands in terms of photons/particle and photons/unit mass of dispersed particles. It is important to note that for each phosphor, spectral regions were specifically chosen to integrate the entire emission bands that were used for thermometry and are indicated by the gray shading on Fig. 4, and the camera exposure time was set to integrate the entire emission decay.

The luminescence signal of ZnO, BAM:Eu²⁺, SMP:Sn²⁺ and MFG:Mn⁴⁺ particles is very similar in dispersed form for the same excitation fluence. Clearly for this application it is important to characterise the materials in the dispersed state because the signal of ZnO relative to BAM:Eu²⁺ in the bulk powder would indicate it is of no use for fluid thermometry (Fig. 2), where in fact both phosphors have already been characterised [14, 15] and successfully used for thermometry in various applications in liquids and gas flows (see Ref. [11] and references therein). Note that the signal per particle in liquid dispersions measured using the spectrometer system is consistent with previous results obtained in phosphor-air aerosols [14, 15]. With an increase in temperature, the emission band of BAM:Eu²⁺

and SMP:Sn²⁺ shifts and broadens towards the shorter wavelength region [15, 20], while that of ZnO broadens towards the longer wavelength region [14]. Those responses were exploited for 2-D fluid thermometry using a two-colour emission detection. For MFG:Mn⁴⁺ two temperature responses can be exploited. The lifetime of the total emission decreases with temperature, which was used for surface thermometry [29, 30]. Two-colour imaging via the ratio of the 630 nm to 660 nm emission was used for fluid thermometry, although it is less sensitive to temperature than the lifetime approach [31, 32]. Although the integrated signal level of MFG:Mn⁴⁺ is similar to BAM:Eu²⁺, ZnO and SMP:Sn²⁺, the lifetime is orders of magnitude higher, at about 3 ms at room temperature. In fluid thermometry the measurement integration time is limited by the flow timescale, which in turbulent gas flows could be 10's μ s or even lower. Under these conditions the MFG:Mn⁴⁺ signal would be reduced by more than an order of magnitude.

Next we consider the the rare-earth ions Dy³⁺ and Pr³⁺ doped into Y₃Al₅O₁₂ hosts. YAG:Dy³⁺ has been investigated by several groups for two-colour gas temperature imaging using the ⁴I_{15/2} → ⁶H_{15/2} emission at 450 nm which increases above 300 K relative to the ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{15/2} emission band in the 480-500 nm spectral region shown in Fig. 4. YAG:Dy³⁺ has a lifetime on the millisecond timescale. Even using a factor 30 higher fluence, this phosphor emits a factor 40 less photons per particle than BAM:Eu²⁺, ZnO, SMP:Sn²⁺ and MFG:Mn⁴⁺. These data are consistent with Refs. [33, 34], which recorded insufficient signal levels in YAG:Dy³⁺ for fluid thermometry. For YAG:Pr³⁺, the ratio of two emission lines is exploited for thermometry: the ¹D₂ → ³H₄ emission line at 610 nm, which has a lifetime of 190 μ s; and the ³P₁ → ³H₄ emission at 480 nm, which has a lifetime of 14 μ s. The integrated visible YAG:Pr³⁺ emission at room temperature is more than an order of magnitude weaker than the brightest phosphors investigated in this study, even at a laser fluence of 500 mJ/cm², because much of the emission is via allowed 4f5d-4f luminescence between 300-350 nm which is typically not used for thermometry. Note that for both YAG-based phosphors, a significant broadband signal was observed in the 425-480 nm region which is probably caused by the very high fluence. It is clear that especially under the restrictions of a short (~10 μ s) exposure time, MFG:Mn⁴⁺, YAG:Dy³⁺ and YAG:Pr³⁺ all exhibit very low signal levels relative to BAM:Eu²⁺, ZnO and SMP:Sn²⁺. Alternatively, YAG:Ce³⁺ should offer high signal levels due to its favourable thermal quenching characteristics and short lifetime (60 ns at 300 K [35]). However, the emission spectrum only weakly depends on temperature, and so it was not used for thermometry [36]. Instead, co-doping YAG with Ce³⁺ and Pr³⁺ was proposed in order to exploit the temperature-dependent ratio of the Pr³⁺ and Ce³⁺ luminescence emissions [37]. The emission intensity of YAG:Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺ and other phosphors employing this interesting thermometry strategy should be measured in the future.

La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ has been used for lifetime-based thermometry in liquid films [38] and droplets [31, 39, 40]. The ⁵D₂ → ⁷F₃ emission line at 512 nm has a lifetime of 12 μ s and at room temperature it is already under the influence of strong thermal

quenching [41], making it useful for highly-sensitive measurements in a temperature range relevant to biology and human comfort e.g. heating and cooling systems. As shown in Fig. 4 the measurements of dispersed particles indicate that this line cannot be detected using our system when using a fluence of 20 mJ/cm². Using the signal of the ⁵D₁ → ⁷F₁ emission at 537 nm and its ratio to the 512 nm emission of approximately a factor 14 at 290 K [28], the signal is 1.4×10³ photons/particle. This is impractically low for temperature imaging in gases using any reasonable seeding density, but in liquids using higher seeding densities, larger particles, larger probe volumes, higher laser fluence and/or optics with high collection efficiency and sensitive photomultiplier tubes, it is possible to take advantage of its high temperature sensitivity.

This dispersed-particle signal data is essential for researchers planning to use these phosphors for thermometry, allowing advance prediction of signal levels and rational design of experiments. Moreover, these signal per particle results provide benchmark comparative data for the future development of temperature sensors. The data is available as supplementary material to this article.

4. Conclusions

Our objective was to develop appropriate characterisation methods to probe the luminescence properties of phosphor particles in order to develop new and more efficient materials and broaden the scope of their application. The luminescence emission intensity is one such property of critical importance. This work clearly demonstrated that relative luminescence signal levels of different phosphor particles obtained from studies of aggregate powder samples does not correspond (by several orders of magnitude) to the relative signal of the same materials when probed as dilute liquid dispersions. In the first case, an “infinitely thick” powder sample, the luminescence signal is dominated by the quantum efficiency of the phosphor and the results are not transferable to the case of optically thin phosphor layers or dispersed particles. Instead, a quantitative per mass comparison performed on dispersed particles also includes the effect of individual particle absorption, which is far more relevant to applications involving optically thin arrangements of particles, such as superresolution microscopy applications in biology, flexible displays, thin coatings etc.

Studying liquid dispersions is a useful technique for rapidly screening the signal level of phosphor particles, but the measured mass is not reliable without careful stabilisation of the mixture. Particle counting is a valuable tool to validate the dispersion stability, and it can also be used to obtain the luminescence signal of an individual phosphor particle independent of any knowledge of the particle size, size distribution or shape.

The characterisation system was used to provide quantitative spectrally-resolved data of dispersed phosphor particles previously employed for fluid thermometry. When using phosphors for temperature measurements in gas flows, both a short luminescence lifetime and high luminescence signal are essential. In this context, BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇:Eu²⁺, ZnO and (Sr,Mg)₃(PO₄)₂:Sn²⁺ offer superior performance compared to Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Dy³⁺, Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Pr³⁺

Figure 4: Quantitative luminescence spectra in terms of photons/particle/nm for $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, ZnO , $(\text{Sr,Mg})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2:\text{Sn}^{2+}$, $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$, $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$, $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$. The spectral resolution is 3.5 nm. The integrated emission bands used for the data in Table 3 are shown.

and $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$. We are applying these characterisation methods for quantitative, comparative studies of luminescent materials to gain fundamental insights into laser-particle interactions. We emphasise that the development of new phosphor-based temperature sensors requires evaluation of the basic temperature sensitivity of the bulk material *and* quantification of the luminescence signal in a state of aggregation that is relevant to the application.

Supplementary material

Quantitative spectral data (photons/nm/particle) for $\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, ZnO , $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$, $(\text{Sr,Mg})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2:\text{Sn}^{2+}$, $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$, $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$ are available online.

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Phosphor	dopant concentration (mol ratio)	particle size μm	luminescence lifetime	Excitation wavelength (nm)	Laser fluence mJ/cm^2	Signal photons/particle	Signal photons/mg
$\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$	Eu/Ba=0.137	2.4	1 μs	266	20	2.7×10^6	5.3×10^{14}
$(\text{Sr},\text{Mg})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2:\text{Sn}^{2+}$	Sn/P=0.020	1.9	24 μs	266	20	2.3×10^6	2.9×10^{14}
$\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$	Mn/Mg=0.002	2.8	3 ms	266	20	2.7×10^6	5.9×10^{14}
ZnO	-	1.2	<1 ns	266	20	3.0×10^6	4.7×10^{15}
$\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$	Dy/Y=0.040	4.2	1 ms	355	660	6.8×10^4	1.4×10^{13}
$\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$	Pr/Y=0.012	1.8	190 μs ⁽¹⁾	266	500	1.1×10^5	2.2×10^{13}
$\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$	-	3.5	12 μs ⁽²⁾	355	20	1.4×10^3	1.8×10^{11}

¹ Lifetime of $^1\text{D}_2$ line; ; note that the luminescence signal data is given for integrated visible emission. ² Lifetime of the $^5\text{D}_2 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_3$ at 512 nm; note that the luminescence signal for this line is inferred from measurements of the neighbouring emission at 537 nm [28].

Table 3: Summary of phosphor data and excitation parameters, and total luminescence signal per particle and per dispersed mass of particles in water dispersions.